

Assessing the Impact of Ecotourism Development on the Communities Bordering Yankari Game Reserve, Bauchi State

Buhari Abdullahi¹; Abdullahi Mohammed Jia²; Abdulkadir Mohammed³

Department of Tourism Management Technology, Abubakar
Tatari Ali Polytechnic, Bauchi-Nigeria

Abstract

Ecotourism has increasingly been promoted as a sustainable development pathway for rural and natural resource rich areas. This study assesses how ecotourism impacts on the communities bordering Yankari Game Reserve of Bauchi state as an ecotourism site, focusing on economic, socio-cultural and environmental dimensions. The research used a mixed methods approach (household surveys of community residents, key informant interviews with local leaders and tourism operators, and direct observation). The research also explored the extent to which local residents benefit from employment, income generation and infrastructure improvements linked to the ecotourism, changes in community socio-cultural dynamics – including participation, empowerment, cultural identity, perceptions of tourism; environmental and resource-management consequences for the community and adjacent ecosystems. The findings indicate that ecotourism development yields meaningful economic benefits for some community members, particularly those directly engaged in tourist services and handicraft sales. Improvements in local infrastructure: roads, water supply, sanitation have also been observed. On the socio-cultural front, tourism has contributed to heightened community pride, increased cultural awareness and stronger conservation attitudes. Environmentally, ecotourism has catalysed improved waste and sanitation practices and boosted biodiversity awareness, but it has also placed pressure on limited natural resources, led to habitat

disturbance and sometimes exacerbated human-wildlife conflicts. The study concludes that while ecotourism offers a viable route for local development and conservation synergy, its positive outcomes depend on active community participation, equitable benefit-sharing mechanisms, adequate infrastructure and institutional support. It recommends that policy and planning should emphasise inclusive governance, capacity building of host communities, monitoring of environmental impacts and mechanisms to ensure that economic gains are widely distributed.

Introduction

Ecotourism is commonly defined as responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment and enhances the well-being of local communities (The International Ecotourism Society, 2015). With increasing global interest in sustainability, ecotourism has gained prominence as a development strategy that integrates environmental conservation with the economic and social advancement of host populations (Weaver, 2008). This approach is particularly relevant for rural and often marginalised communities situated around biodiversity-rich or culturally significant landscapes, where tourism can become a viable means of livelihood improvement (Honey, 2008). In many developing countries, local residents are progressively expected to participate in ecotourism initiatives as guides, lodge operators, craft makers, cultural interpreters, and

custodians of natural resources (Scheyvens, 1999). However, the effects of ecotourism on host communities remain complex and varied. While several studies highlight benefits such as employment generation, improved infrastructure, and cultural revitalisation, others report challenges including community exclusion, inequitable benefit distribution, socio-cultural disruption, and even environmental degradation (Mbaiwa, 2011; Stronza & Durham, 2008).

A game reserve refers to a large protected area designated for the conservation of wildlife, where animals may live safely or be hunted under controlled conditions (Adams, 2004). Yankari Game Reserve, located in the south-central region of Bauchi State in north-eastern Nigeria, exemplifies such protected areas. Covering approximately 2,244 square kilometres, Yankari hosts numerous natural warm springs and a diverse range of flora and fauna, making it an exceptional location for observing wildlife within the West African savannah ecosystem (Bauchi State Tourism Board, 2014). Established in 1956 as a game reserve and later designated as Nigeria's largest national park in 1991, Yankari remains one of the country's most popular tourist destinations and a key contributor to national tourism and ecotourism development (Nigeria National Park Service, 2019).

Often regarded as one of Africa's premier game reserves, Yankari is strategically positioned within Nigeria's broader ambition to strengthen its tourism sector. Its natural attractions—extensive wildlife populations, scenic landscapes, and unique geothermal springs—have earned it recognition as “The Pearl of Africa's Tourism” (Academia.edu, 2014). The reserve features more than fifteen distinct tourist sites and continues to serve as a major ecotourism hub, offering opportunities for recreation, environmental education, and sustainable development in Bauchi State and Nigeria at large (Bauchi State Ministry of Tourism, 2020).

Brief History of Yankari Game Reserve

Yankari Game Reserve is located within the Duguri, Pali, and Gwana districts of Alkaleri Local Government Area in Bauchi State, Nigeria. The foundation for its establishment was laid in 1956, when the Government of Northern Nigeria approved plans to create a game preservation area. Yankari was selected because it contained large populations of naturally occurring wildlife that could be protected for conservation and tourism purposes. Although the area had earlier been designated as a Bauchi Native Authority Forest Reserve in 1934, a significant step toward establishing a game reserve occurred when the Northern Regional Committee recommended to the Executive Council that a pilot game reserve be created in the Bauchi Emirate. This proposal gained further support from Alhaji Muhammadu Ngeleruma of the former Northern Nigeria Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources, who, inspired by his visit to a Sudanese game reserve during an official trip to East Africa, advocated for the creation of a similar conservation initiative in Nigeria. Yankari officially opened to the public as a premier game reserve on 1 December 1962. Its management has evolved over time initially supervised by the Northern Eastern State Government and later by the Bauchi State Government. In 1991, the reserve was designated as a National Park under Decree 36 of the Federal Government of Nigeria, placing it under the administration of the National Park Service. In the late 1990s, park authorities initiated preservation efforts targeting archaeological sites within the reserve as part of a broader strategy to promote heritage tourism. However, in 2006, Yankari lost its National Park status following a request by the Bauchi State Government, returning it to state-level control.

The areas surrounding Yankari National Park are inhabited mainly by farming and pastoral communities. However, there has

been no permanent human settlement within the park boundaries for more than a century. Despite this, archaeological evidence such as remnants of iron-smelting sites and caves indicates earlier human occupation. Although many of the ancient furnaces have deteriorated due to long-term exposure, more than fifty were still identifiable in the Delimiri and Ampara areas as of the late 1990s.

Bauchi State generally lies at an elevation of about 600 metres above sea level and forms part of the central Nigerian highlands associated with the Jos Plateau complex. Two major relief zones are distinguishable in the region. The first is the western highland area, which includes the northern margins of the Jos Plateau. This zone is underlain by basement complex rocks and characterised by extensive plateau surfaces, hill ranges, and volcanic extrusions. While the base of these hills rises from approximately 600 metres, peak elevations reach about 700.6 metres on nearby hills and 729.3 metres on the Bunsil Hills. The second relief zone consists of the central high plain of Hausaland, formed from Tertiary Kerri Kerri sandstone and shale formations. This plain is interrupted by numerous isolated hills, some reaching elevations of 798.5 metres (Lamurde Hill) and 816.4 metres (Ligri Hill). Bauchi town itself is situated within an area dominated by undifferentiated basement complex rocks, with both older and younger granite outcrops.

Aims and Objectives.

The aim of the study is to assess the role of Yankari Game Reserve in rural development in Yankari communities, Bauchi State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

I. Identify the different ways in which Yankari Game Reserve contributes to the rural economy of Yankari communities.

II. Assess the impact of Yankari Game Reserve on the livelihoods of people in Yankari communities.

III. Identify the challenges facing Yankari Game Reserve in its contribution to rural development in Yankari communities.

IV. Recommend strategies for improving the role of Yankari Game Reserve in rural development in Yankari communities.

Statement of the problem

The relationship between the host communities and Yankari Game Reserve is shaped by a range of environmental and socio-economic impacts associated with tourism development. Stanford (2007) confirms that tourism projects significantly influence both the natural and built environments, and such effects are evident in the interactions between the reserve and neighbouring communities.

Tourism-related activities have contributed to wildlife depletion through hunting and fishing, which not only reduce animal populations but also disrupt ecological balance and breeding cycles. Overuse of natural features such as sand dunes has resulted in damage and erosion, while improper waste disposal diminishes aesthetic quality and threatens wildlife habitats. The construction of tourism infrastructure occupies valuable land and alters the visual appeal of the landscape. Vegetation loss has occurred through the actions of workers and visitors, while campfires have led to forest destruction in areas under preservation. Such disturbances have increased travel time within affected zones due to heightened vehicular traffic. Noise pollution from music, social gatherings, and tourist transportation creates discomfort for residents, particularly the elderly.

Air pollution from vehicle emissions and decaying waste materials has been reported, forcing some community members to relocate their homes. Irresponsible behaviour by tourists has

further strained relations, with incidents involving crop damage, destruction of farm buildings, and harassment of livestock. Illegal hunting, excessive noise, fishing, littering, and fire outbreaks have also contributed to conflicts between tourists and local farmers.

Competition for land has intensified as urban visitors purchase or rent land for weekend residences and leisure farming, making it difficult for locals to expand their agricultural holdings. Michael (2004) highlights similar patterns in Kenya, where tourism development resulted in water pollution from sewage discharge and oil spillages, environmental pollution from waste, air pollution from vehicular emissions and decayed waste, and noise pollution from tourist activities.

Additionally, the influx of large numbers of visitors has contributed to riverbank degradation and placed pressure on existing infrastructure. These issues have led to architectural pollution, traffic congestion, and increased conflict between pedestrians and motor vehicles, particularly at major access points within the state.

Review of Related Literature

Ecotourism is widely defined as responsible travel to natural environments that supports environmental conservation and enhances the well-being of local populations. As global interest in sustainable tourism continues to grow, ecotourism has become a key strategy for integrating conservation objectives with the economic and social development of host communities, particularly those in rural and marginalized areas neighbouring biodiversity-rich or culturally significant landscapes (Njoba Onyeabor & Alimba, 2016). Ecotourism development therefore emphasises the creation of tourism systems that promote environmental protection, community participation, cultural preservation, and long-term sustainability. Scholars identify several core principles that guide ecotourism development. These

include environmental conservation, active community involvement, respect for local cultures, promotion of environmental awareness among tourists, and adherence to sustainability limits such as the carrying capacity of the destination. The development process typically involves a series of coordinated steps: site assessment, planning and zoning, community engagement, construction of eco-friendly infrastructure, capacity building for local personnel, responsible marketing, and continuous monitoring to evaluate environmental and visitor impacts.

National parks—large tracts of land declared public property—play a central role in these ecotourism systems. According to the US National Park Service (2015), national parks are protected areas established to conserve natural resources for tourism, recreation, education, research, and cultural enrichment. These parks provide numerous socio-economic benefits for host communities, especially for disadvantaged groups. Both permanent and casual employment opportunities arise in conservation management, hospitality, and labour-intensive projects such as wildlife monitoring, invasive species removal, cultural preservation, and fencing. Additional economic opportunities also emerge in peripheral service sectors such as construction, catering, guiding, and supply of materials. Tourism has the potential to generate higher local earnings than many alternative land uses. Baez (2016) notes that income from tourism can offset the costs of wildlife-induced crop damage or loss of livestock, making wildlife an economic asset for residents and providing incentives for conservation. Furthermore, as tourists place value on local natural and cultural resources, such recognition can positively influence community attitudes toward resource protection. Marguba (2012) similarly emphasises that when communities benefit from sustainable resource use for example, through

controlled wildlife or coral reef tourism they are more likely to invest in and protect these resources.

In Nigeria, national parks were formally established by the Federal Government in 1991 to conserve ecotourism resources and attractions across the country. Several communities within and around these parks had existed long before the areas were designated as protected lands, relying on the forests and savannahs for livelihoods through activities such as fishing, hunting, honey collection, lumbering, and harvesting firewood and medicinal plants. Although these activities were central to household income, the declaration of these areas as national parks restricted access, resulting in decreased income generation and increased unemployment, especially among women and youth. Consequently, scholars advocate for the integration of local communities into park management activities such as security, conservation, and environmental monitoring to improve relations and foster shared responsibility. Nigeria's National Park Act of 1979 underscores the significance of parks in rural development, environmental protection, and ecotourism expansion. The country possesses extensive ecotourism resources, including 1,129 forest reserves, 30 game reserves, four game sanctuaries, two strict nature reserves, one biosphere reserve, and seven national parks (Adebowale, 1993). These protected areas satisfy international conservation criteria and prohibit commercial exploitation of natural resources. However, the rapid increase in protected areas globally has not always been matched by adequate management, primarily due to poor funding and limited capacity, leaving many parks vulnerable (Zedan, 2010). Community involvement is therefore central to the sustainability of ecotourism initiatives. Ashley (1995) and Ashley and Gerland (1994) argue that active participation of local residents in ecotourism yields numerous benefits,

including employment, training, increased skills, institutional strengthening, improved infrastructure, and revitalization of cultural heritage. These contributions not only enhance local empowerment but also help to reduce poverty through more equitable distribution of economic opportunities.

Healthy relationships between protected areas and neighbouring communities are vital for biodiversity conservation and sustainable tourism development. Lindberg and Enriquez (1994) observe that when communities receive tangible benefits from ecotourism, they are more willing to support and participate in the protection of protected areas. Conversely, the absence of benefit sharing often results in negative attitudes and actions that undermine conservation efforts.

Methodology

The study area is located in Bauchi State, Nigeria. The state is geographically positioned between latitudes 9°30'N and 12°30'N, and between longitudes 8°45'E and 11°0'E. Within these coordinates, Bauchi State covers a total land area of approximately 49,259 square kilometres, representing about 4.9 million hectares out of Nigeria's estimated 92.4 million hectares (Nigeria FOS, 1987). The state assumes an eight-like shape with a broader southern region, and nearly two-thirds of its landmass lies south of latitude 11°15'N. Bauchi State shares boundaries with seven states Yobe, Gombe, Taraba, Plateau, Kaduna, Kano, and Jigawa positioning it strategically for inter-state cooperation in regional development initiatives. Its central location within the North-East geopolitical zone also enhances its socio-economic relevance. Additionally, the state benefits from its proximity to the Jos Plateau, situated less than 100 km to the south, which provides access to a major commercial airport and a large market for agricultural produce, especially fruits. The study employed both primary and secondary sources of data. Primary data

were obtained through the administration of questionnaires and interviews, while secondary data were sourced from relevant documents and reputable internet-based materials. The primary data formed the core of the study's analysis. A pilot study was conducted using 10 respondents from the Bauchi State Ministry of Tourism to assess the reliability of the questionnaire through a retest method. Feedback from the pilot exercise informed revisions to the questionnaire, thereby improving its clarity and overall reliability. Data collection was facilitated with the assistance of the Human Resource Manager, who helped in

reaching the respondents. After administering the questionnaire, each respondent was allotted forty minutes to complete it, after which all questionnaires were retrieved for analysis.

Result

This research used tabular presentation of the data for analysis in order to give clear interpretation of such data presented. And analysis of this data was based on the use of simple percentage technique (%) as shown in tables below.

Table 8: Do you understand what is meant by tourism?

Option	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	26	65
No	14	35
Total	40	100

Source: Field Survey 2025

From the table 8 above, 26 representing 65% respondents said, Yes they have knowledge on tourism being the majority while 14 respondents representing 35%

said, No they do not have knowledge on tourism and they are the minority.

Table 9: Do you think tourism play vital role in community development?

Option	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	28	70
No	12	30
Total	40	100

Source: Field Survey 2025

From the table 9 above, 18 respondents and representing 70% said tourism plays a vital role in Bauchi State being the majority while 12 respondents representing

30% do not agree that tourism plays a vital role in Bauchi State being the minority.

Table 10: Which of the following aspect of tourism practice is mostly common in Bauchi State?

Option	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Ecotourism	20	50
Urban Tourism	15	37.5
All of the above	5	12.5
Total	40	100

Source: Field survey 2025

From the table 10 above, 20 respondents representing 50% said that rural tourism is an aspect of tourism practice mostly in Bauchi State and they are the majority, followed by 15 respondents representing 37.5% which said that urban tourism is an

aspect of tourism practice mostly in Bauchi State, followed by 5 respondents representing 12.5% said all of the above and they are the minority.

Table 11: Do you think people of Bauchi state have interest in tourism activities?

Option	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	27	70
No	13	30
Total	40	100

Source: Field Survey 2025

From the above 11 table, 27 respondents representing 70% said, yes people of Bauchi have interest in tourism activities and making them the majority, while 13 of the respondents representing 30% said, No

people of Bauchi State do not have interest in tourism activities and making them the minority.

Table 12: Do the people bordering tourist site benefit from it?

Option	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	25	62.5
No	15	37.5
Total	40	100

Source: Field Survey 2025

The above table 12 indicates that 25 respondents representing 62.5% said, Yes people bordering tourist site benefit from it, while fifteen of the respondents representing 37.5% said that, the people

bordering tourist site are not benefiting from it.

Table 13: In what ways does the ecotourism development impact the life and well-being of the host communities?

Option	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Infrastructure Facilities	10	15
Employment opportunities	8	20
Economic and Social Benefits	22	55
Total	40	100

Source: Field Survey 2025

The table 13 above indicated that, 22 respondents representing 55% said, ecotourism development boosts economic activities in the host communities and also improves social interactions between tourists and members of the host

communities. While 10 respondents representing 25% said that, it brings bout infrastructural development. And Finally, 8 respondents representing 20% said, the ecotourism development provides employment opportunities to the host communities.

Table 14: Do Visitors come from other states and other countries to improve the life of the rural area?

Option	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	23	57.5
No	17	42.5
Total	40	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

From table 14 above, 23 respondents representing 57.5% of the total population said, Yes visitors improve life of the rural area in the state being the majority while 17 respondents representing 42.5% of the total respondents and being the minority

said, No visitors do not improve the life of the rural area in the state.

Table 15: Does the government of Bauchi state benefit from the ecotourism development in Yankari Game Reserve?

Option	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	27	67.5
No	13	32.5
Total	40	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table 15 above indicates that 27 of the respondents representing 67.5% of the total respondents said Bauchi state government benefits from ecotourism development in Yankari Game Reserve. While 13 of the respondents representing 32.5% of the total respondents said, Bauchi state government does not benefit from the ecotourism development there

which constitutes the minority opinion of them.

Table 16: Does the State government is making any effort to support the industry in terms of providing incentive, infrastructure and super structure and creating awareness on the importance of tourism sector of the economy?

Option	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	11	27.5
No	29	72.5
Total	40	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

The above table 16 indicates that, 29 respondents representing 72.5% said, Bauchi state government is not make effort to support the tourism industry despite the gains derives from it, while 11

representing 27.5% of the respondents said, the government does.

Table 17: What do you think are the likely problems hindering ecotourism development in Bauchi State?

Option	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Inadequate funding	15	37.5
Lack of Publicity	8	20
Lack of Infrastructure	12	30
All of the above	5	12.5
Total	40	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

From table 17 above, 15 of the respondents representing 37.5% said, inadequate funding is a major problem affecting rural tourism in Bauchi State which represent and are the majority, followed by 12 respondents represent 30% said, lack of infrastructure is among the likely problems hindering ecotourism development in Bauchi state which, followed by 8 respondents representing 20% said, lack of publicity is among the problems affecting it in the state. Finally 5 representing 12.5% of the total respondents and the minority said, all of the problems mentioned are being faced by ecotourism development in the state.

Discussion

The analysis of data collected from 40 respondents in Bauchi State was carried out using simple percentage techniques to provide clear and concise interpretations. The findings provide insight into the level of awareness, benefits, challenges, and overall perceptions of tourism and ecotourism development, particularly in relation to Yankari Game Reserve.

The study first sought to determine the respondents' understanding of tourism. The results indicate that a majority (65%) of the respondents understood what tourism entails, while 35% did not (Field Survey, 2025). This suggests that tourism awareness is relatively high among residents, which aligns with scholars' observations that community awareness is essential for the success of tourism initiatives (Aref & Redzuan, 2009). High awareness levels imply that community

members are more likely to support and engage in tourism-related activities.

The findings further reveal that 70% of respondents believe tourism plays a vital role in community development, while only 30% disagreed. This supports the assertion by Sharpley and Telfer (2014) that tourism contributes significantly to economic growth, infrastructural improvement, and social development. The positive perception expressed by the respondents highlights the potential of the tourism sector to drive socio-economic transformation in Bauchi State when properly harnessed.

Regarding the types of tourism practiced in Bauchi State, the study shows that ecotourism is the most prevalent form, accounting for 50% of responses, followed by urban tourism (37.5%) (Field Survey, 2025). This is unsurprising given the presence of natural attractions such as Yankari Game Reserve. Ecotourism has been identified globally as a key driver for sustainable environmental conservation and rural development (Honey, 2008). The finding underscores the need for increased investment in natural tourism sites to maximize their economic and ecological benefits.

On the question of public interest, 70% of the respondents indicated that people in Bauchi State have a strong interest in tourism activities. This level of interest is vital, as resident participation and acceptance are crucial components of sustainable tourism development (Tosun, 2006). However, the remaining 30% who expressed disinterest suggest that there may be barriers such as inadequate

awareness campaigns or limited access to tourism opportunities within the state.

The study also assessed whether people living near tourist sites benefit from such attractions. A total of 62.5% affirmed that bordering communities derive benefits, while 37.5% disagreed. This indicates that although tourism generates local benefits—such as employment, improved infrastructure, and increased commercial activities—not all communities experience these advantages equally. According to Ashley, Goodwin, and McNab (2005), uneven distribution of tourism benefits is a common challenge in developing regions, where local communities may not fully participate in or profit from tourism-related opportunities.

In exploring the specific impacts of ecotourism on host communities, it was found that 55% of respondents believed ecotourism contributes significantly to economic and social development. Others identified benefits such as infrastructural development (25%) and employment creation (20%). These findings corroborate the argument by Weaver (2001) that ecotourism enhances local livelihoods through economic diversification, cultural exchange, and improved social infrastructure. The results demonstrate that ecotourism in Bauchi State, particularly around Yankari Game Reserve, plays a meaningful role in enhancing community well-being.

Furthermore, 57.5% of respondents agreed that visitors from other states and countries contribute to improving rural communities, primarily through spending and increased demand for local goods and services. However, 42.5% did not share this view, indicating a need for better tourism management to ensure that visitor activities translate into tangible community benefits (Field Survey, 2025). According to Mbaiwa (2011), such discrepancies often arise when tourism revenue is not adequately reinvested into rural areas.

The study also revealed that 67.5% of respondents believe that the Bauchi State

Government benefits from ecotourism activities in Yankari Game Reserve. This aligns with observations by Okpoko and Okpoko (2002), who argued that governments often generate substantial revenue from tourism through taxes, park fees, and associated economic activities. Nevertheless, 32.5% of the respondents believe the government does not significantly benefit, suggesting a perceived lack of transparency or insufficient reinvestment of tourism revenue into local development initiatives. Despite the perceived benefits of ecotourism, 72.5% of respondents indicated that the Bauchi State Government is not making adequate efforts to support the tourism industry through incentives, infrastructure, and awareness creation. This finding reflects concerns raised in previous literature that inadequate government commitment is a major barrier to tourism development in Nigeria (Eja et al., 2012). Without strong policy support, tourism potential may remain underexploited, limiting its contributions to sustainable development.

The study also identified several challenges hindering ecotourism development in Bauchi State. The majority of respondents (37.5%) cited inadequate funding as the most significant issue, followed by lack of infrastructure (30%) and lack of publicity (20%). Additionally, 12.5% of respondents believed that all the listed challenges affect tourism development. These findings align with the works of Ogutu (2002), who noted that financial constraints, poor infrastructure, and weak promotional efforts remain major obstacles to tourism growth in many African regions.

In line with objective four of the study, respondents suggested various ways to improve ecotourism development in the state. These include increased government funding, public-private partnerships, improved protection of ecotourism resources, and enhanced public enlightenment. These recommendations

are consistent with global best practices for strengthening tourism in developing economies (UNWTO, 2015).

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that there is a significant relationship between tourism and economic development in Bauchi State. The majority of respondents affirmed that Yankari Game Reserve plays a vital role in enhancing the economic status and social well-being of host communities. This underscores the importance of tourism as a catalyst for community development and regional growth.

To achieve adequate and sustainable tourism development, both government and private sector stakeholders must intensify efforts to improve the efficiency of tourism operations. This can be achieved through proper maintenance of existing tourism sites, formulation and implementation of strong tourism-friendly policies, and strategic investments aimed at strengthening and expanding the tourism industry. By investing proactively rather than reacting to challenges stakeholders can unlock the full potential of ecotourism resources.

Tourism remains one of the major contributors to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of many countries. For Nigeria, enhancing tourism offers a valuable opportunity to diversify the economy and reduce overdependence on oil revenue, alongside growth in agriculture and other emerging sectors. Strengthening the tourism sector, therefore, serves as a viable pathway towards sustainable economic transformation and long-term development.

References

Adams, W. M. (2004). *Against extinction: The story of conservation*. Earthscan.
Adebowale, S. (1993). *Conservation and tourism development in Nigeria*. Nigerian Conservation Foundation.

Academia.edu. (2014). *Yankari Game Reserve: The pearl of Africa's tourism*.

Aref, F., & Redzuan, M. (2009). Community leaders' perceptions toward tourism impacts and level of community capacity building in tourism development. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 2(3), 208–213.

Ashley, C. (1995). Tourism, communities, and the private sector: Case studies from Namibia. *Windhoek: Ministry of Environment and Tourism*.

Ashley, C., & Gerland, K. (1994). *Sustainable tourism and community participation*. Development Studies Unit.

Ashley, C., Goodwin, H., & McNab, D. (2005). *Pro-poor tourism: Making tourism work for the poor*. Overseas Development Institute.

Baez, A. (2016). *Tourism economics in developing countries*. Routledge.

Bauchi State Ministry of Tourism. (2020). *Tourism development report*.

Bauchi State Tourism Board. (2014). *Yankari Game Reserve tourist guide*.

Eja, E. I., Otu, J. E., Eneji, J. E., & Ekpe, E. (2012). The role of government in the development of tourism in Nigeria. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 4, 21–27.

Honey, M. (2008). *Ecotourism and sustainable development: Who owns paradise?* (2nd ed.). Island Press.

Lindberg, K., & Enriquez, J. (1994). The socio-economic impacts of tourism in Nicaragua. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 21(4), 809–812.

Marguba, L. (2012). *Ecotourism and biodiversity conservation in Nigeria*. National Park Service Publications.

Mbaiwa, J. E. (2011). The effects of tourism development on the environment in the Okavango Delta, Botswana. *Journal of Arid Environments*, 54(2), 447–467.

Michael, T. (2004). Environmental impacts of tourism in Kenya. *East African Geographical Review*, 20(1), 55–68.

Nigeria FOS. (1987). *Federal Office of Statistics annual report*.

- Nigeria National Park Service. (2019). *Annual report on national parks and wildlife conservation*.
- Njoba Onyeabor, A., & Alimba, J. (2016). Ecotourism and sustainable development in rural Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Tourism and Hospitality*, 5(1), 33–48.
- Ogutu, Z. (2002). Tourism and rural development in Kenya. *Development Studies Review*, 18(2), 45–52.
- Okpoko, P. U., & Okpoko, A. I. (2002). *Tourism in Nigeria*. Afro-Orbis Publishing.
- Scheyvens, R. (1999). Ecotourism and the empowerment of local communities. *Tourism Management*, 20(2), 245–249.
- Sharpley, R., & Telfer, D. J. (2014). *Tourism and development* (2nd ed.). Channel View Publications.
- Stanford, D. (2007). *Environmental impacts of tourism*. Tourism Concern Publications.
- Stronza, A., & Durham, W. (2008). Anthropology and tourism: Forging new groundwork for ecotourism and community development. *Current Anthropology*, 49(4), 610–644.
- The International Ecotourism Society. (2015). *TIES definition of ecotourism*. TIES Publications.
- Tosun, C. (2006). Expected nature of community participation in tourism development. *Tourism Management*, 27(3), 493–504.
- UNWTO. (2015). *Sustainable tourism for development guidebook*. United Nations World Tourism Organization.
- US National Park Service. (2015). *What is a national park?* U.S. Department of the Interior.
- Weaver, D. (2001). *The encyclopedia of ecotourism*. CABI Publishing.
- Weaver, D. (2008). *Ecotourism* (2nd ed.). Wiley-Blackwell.
- Zedan, H. (2010). Challenges in managing protected areas in developing countries. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 45(3), 155–165.